

Advancing Nuclear Education in Texas: Graduate Program Development at Abilene Christian University

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ABSTRACT

Abilene Christian University (ACU) is launching a graduate program in Nuclear Science and Engineering that combines rigorous coursework with hands-on reactor experience. The program will offer M.S., M.Eng., and Ph.D. pathways centered on research with ACU's Molten Salt Research Reactor and the NEXT Laboratory. Students will gain skills in reactor physics, radiation transport, fuel cycle analysis, and risk-informed decision making, with an emphasis on ethical leadership and job-ready competencies. The curriculum emphasizes core topics, and the program plans to support a concentration in radiation protection and health physics in the future to further meet workforce needs. Further expansion will include certificate-based training modules. This initiative will contribute to a statewide effort to expand nuclear education, scale training pipelines and prepare instructors to empower Texans. Supported by recent Texas legislation, institutional investment and partnerships, the program is being built to supply industry, national labs, and regulators with technically strong, operationally experienced graduates and eventually certificate-style training for regional needs.

Keywords: Graduate Nuclear Education, Molten Salt Reactor, Advanced Reactor Training

1. INTRODUCTION

Texas is moving fast on advanced nuclear deployment, and Abilene Christian University (ACU) is stepping up to train the people who will build and operate it. Our new graduate program in Nuclear Science and Engineering (NS&E) pairs rigorous coursework with hands-on research with the Molten Salt Research Reactor (MSRR) [1] and the Nuclear Energy eXperimental Testing Laboratory (NEXT Lab) [2]. The mission of ACU's NEXT Lab is to provide global solutions to the world's needs for energy, water, and medical isotopes by advancing molten salt reactor technologies and educating future leaders in nuclear science and engineering [3]. Meanwhile, the MSRR aims to accelerate the development and deployment of molten salt reactor systems through foundational research and fostering a pipeline for a nuclear-qualified workforce. ACU's substantial investment in the MSRR will establish a world-class molten salt research facility, actively used by students, staff, faculty, and outside collaborators, to conduct research on molten salt systems and to develop a new generation of engineers and scientists—uniquely prepared to contribute to advancements in molten salt reactors and related applications [4].

This effort is reinforced by recent Texas legislation that creates funding and workforce pathways for advanced nuclear technology; specifically, Texas House Bill 14 (2025) and Texas Senate Bill 1535 (2025) provide deployment funding, establish a state advanced nuclear office, and direct workforce development and credentialing for the sector [5, 6], and appropriate \$120 million to support the MSRR project [7]. ACU's program leverages those state priorities and our MSRR and NEXT investments to deliver job-ready skills:

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- reactor physics,
- radiation transport,
- fuel-cycle analysis,
- risk-informed decision making,

while emphasizing ethical leadership and operational competency. ACU appointed the program's Founding Director, Dr. Mark DeHart, in June 2025, a key milestone in its graduate expansion [8]. Shortly thereafter, the first curriculum proposals and course frameworks were drafted, initiating formal review through the university's academic program approval process. These early efforts focused on aligning instructional design with ACU's research infrastructure and the broader goals of workforce development and interdisciplinary rigor. Dr. James Drachenberg has recently joined the program in a part time capacity as the Graduate Curriculum Coordinator. Together, DeHart and Drachenberg seek to develop a program that reflects ACU's commitment to integrating technical rigor with principled leadership, fostering a sense of service, integrity, and responsible stewardship of nuclear technology, preparing graduates to contribute meaningfully to innovation and public trust.

The NS&E program is part of a broader institutional commitment to Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) growth under the leadership of President Dr. Phil Schubert. During his tenure, ACU has launched the NEXT Lab, completed a more than \$50 million expansion of science and engineering facilities [9, 10], and achieved Carnegie R2 research status in 2025 [11]. This represents an academic milestone that reflects increased investment in graduate education and STEM research capacity. STEM programs at ACU are housed within the Robert and Kay Onstead College of Science and Engineering, which includes departments in engineering, physics, mathematics, biology, chemistry, and environmental sciences. The NS&E program builds on this foundation, contributing to ACU's five-year trajectory of expanding graduate offerings, supporting undergraduate research through Undergraduate Research, Creativity, and Innovation (URCI) grants, and positioning the university as a hub for advanced nuclear education and workforce development. The NS&E program will offer the first graduate degrees in the College of Science and Engineering and the first Ph.D at ACU. It is hoped that this will be the starting point for more graduate programs in the STEM fields.

In the context of Texas's expanding nuclear policy landscape, ACU's educational program development plans offer a timely and scalable response to workforce needs. This paper presents the program's structure, curricular philosophy, and strategic vision, with emphasis on its alignment to state priorities, its phased development, and its long-term goal of offering certificate-based training for regional industrial deployments.

2. PROGRAM RATIONALE AND NEEDS ANALYSIS

Advanced reactor projects need qualified people, and they need them now; workforce shortages threaten timelines, budgets, and safety, and Texas will require over 10,000 skilled workers by the early 2030s to support deployment, with critical gaps in construction trades, nuclear technicians, and operations staff [12]. ACU's NS&E program addresses that gap by training students in reactor physics, radiation protection, operational protocols, and computational methods and by verifying competencies through MSRR-based lab work and applied capstones. Graduates will need less on-the-job training, reduce employer risk, and accelerate safe, locally sourced deployment while the program's certificate pathways provide knowledge/skills upgrades for industry and shorten the time from classroom to competent worksite contribution.

This graduate program addresses an urgent need for technically skilled, operationally experienced nuclear professionals. Rapid shifts in policy, market activity, and private investment, paired with Texas legislative support for advanced nuclear deployment, are producing demand for practitioners who can move from classroom concepts to hands-on reactor operations, modeling and simulation, and risk-informed decision making. ACU's program is structured so that so each credential maps directly to

employer needs, and professional certificates will allow retraining of current workers to meet the needs of the advanced reactor industry:

- the professional M.Eng. prepares graduate for immediate engineering practice and project leadership,
- the M.S. will equip candidates for applied research and R&D roles,
- the Ph.D. aims to develop independent scholars and senior technical leaders.

This credential differentiation enables straightforward alignment between student pathways and hiring markets across utilities, vendors, national laboratories, and regulatory agencies.

Significant state funding, along with recent institutional investments, position ACU to meet this demand: the \$120 million secured through the efforts of state leaders provides critical support to the Molten Salt Research Reactor, anticipated to start operations in 2026 [13], the NEXT Lab, expanded science facilities at the new Science and Engineering Research Center [14], three science facilities: Onstead Science Center, Halbert Walling Research Center and Bennett Labs. [15], as well as Carnegie R2 status together create a practical foundation for a new graduate-based program in science and engineering. Those assets, combined with a phased faculty hiring plan and early use of dual-listed offerings and adjunct coverage where needed, will provide a credible route to launch a competitive curriculum quickly while building longer-term research capacity. The program's emphasis on hands-on learning, competency-based assessment, and principled leadership further distinguishes it from programs that rely primarily on classroom or simulation work; it addresses employer preferences for graduates who can demonstrate verified lab competencies and documented experience.

The NS&E plan addresses key risks of accreditation delays, enrollment uncertainty, and research funding variability through:

- staged hiring tied to pro forma milestones,
- diversified revenue streams:
 - initial university support,
 - grants,
 - philanthropy,
 - future training certifications,
- contingency instructional models:
 - adjunct faculty,
 - dual-listed courses.

Admissions timing and cohort planning are being aligned with anticipated employer needs and licensure pathways so graduates enter the workforce as demand peaks. Taken together, the regional workforce need, favorable policy environment, and institutional resources make a compelling case for launching ACU's NS&E graduate program: the university can rapidly produce high-value graduates who meet the practical and near-term demands of a growing nuclear sector while scaling responsibly as funding, accreditation, and faculty capacity mature.

3. PROGRAM DESIGN

The proposed curriculum will emphasize core topics that include reactor physics, radiation transport, fuel cycle analysis, nuclear risk management, and responsible leadership. Students in the M.S. and M.Eng. programs will complete foundational coursework and a thesis or applied project experience, while Ph.D. students progress through qualifying milestones, independent research, and a dissertation defense.

To meet workforce needs, ACU will introduce a concentration in radiation protection and health physics once the reactor-focused track stabilizes. We will expand with certificate-based training modules aligned to regional deployments, targeting reactor operations, safeguards, and radiological safety.

ACU's graduate program directly supports the Texas tri-agency strategy led by the Texas Workforce Commission, Texas Education Agency, and Texas Higher Education Coordinating Board, as mandated by SB 1535 and HB 14. By offering reactor-based training, future concentrations in radiation protection and health physics, and plans for certificate-based modules tailored to regional industrial needs, ACU plans to contribute to a statewide effort to expand nuclear education access, scale training pipelines, and prepare instructors for high-demand roles. The program seeks not only to educate, but to empower Texans to contribute to a well-planned and sustainable energy future, leveraging the potential of nuclear science to meet anticipated energy needs.

4. CURRICULUM AND COURSE HIGHLIGHTS

The NS&E curriculum balances foundational rigor with research-centered flexibility, supporting students across M.S., M.Eng., and Ph.D pathways. Initial course offerings will focus on core competencies in reactor physics, radiation transport, nuclear fuel cycle analysis, and risk-informed decision making, with integrated emphasis on ethical leadership and real-world application. Elective options will expand over time to include specialized topics in radiation protection, health physics, and nuclear systems modeling.

To support both instruction and research, ACU is implementing a phased faculty hiring plan that prioritizes expertise in reactor operations, radiation measurement, and computational analysis. Early hires will develop and deliver core graduate courses and mentor student research tied to the MSRR and NEXT Lab. As the program grows, additional faculty will be recruited to support emerging concentrations and certificate-based training modules.

Graduate coursework will incorporate analytic verification, coding fluency, and modeling techniques throughout the curriculum, preparing students to engage with modern reactor design, safety analysis, and regulatory frameworks. These skills are embedded in both core and elective offerings, ensuring that students develop the computational literacy and quantitative reasoning required for advanced nuclear roles. To broaden elective availability during program startup, ACU will offer dual-listed undergraduate/graduate courses in mathematics and physics, enabling students to deepen their technical foundation while fulfilling degree requirements. Graduate students enrolled in these courses will complete additional assignments, advanced problem sets, and graduate-level content to ensure appropriate academic rigor. Faculty from various departments will collaborate to ensure the courses remain relevant and aligned with program goals. Table I provides an overview of the planned programs.

5. STUDENT PATHWAYS, PARTNERSHIPS, AND OUTCOMES

Students enter NS&E through three routes: direct Ph.D. admission from a bachelor's, internal progression from the M.S., or Ph.D. transfer with an earned M.S., serving recent graduates and mid-career professionals. The professional M.Eng. is conceived as a standalone, project-oriented credential focused on applied engineering and is not part of the standard Ph.D. progression; however, M.Eng. students may, with approval from the Program Director and a formal review of their coursework and research readiness, transition into the Ph.D. pathway. Each route is governed by clear milestones: core course completion, continuous seminar participation, proposal/qualifying examinations where applicable, documented laboratory credits, and committee reviews, so students and advisors can map an efficient, goal-aligned flow from coursework to independent research or professional practice.

Pathways are optimized for different career goals. The M.Eng. is oriented toward industry readiness and culminates in a project-based capstone that demonstrates systems integration, regulatory awareness, and deliverable management. The M.S. balances advanced coursework with a research thesis, preparing students for industry R&D or transition to doctoral research. The Ph.D. emphasizes sustained, original scholarship carried out in ACU's reactor and experimental facilities and partner labs, with expectations for qualifying examinations, a formal dissertation proposal, and peer-reviewable out-

Table I. ACU Nuclear Science and Engineering: Planned Curriculum Map

Category	MS	M.Eng.	Ph.D
Core Courses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to Nuclear Engineering • Nuclear Reactor Theory • Reactor Thermal Hydraulics • Reactor Design • Radiation Detection and Measurement • Seminar • Research Hours 	Same as M.S., with emphasis on applied design and systems integration	Same as M.S., plus advanced research methods and qualifying exam prep
Electives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Linear Algebra • Numerical Methods • Machine Learning • Nuclear Chemistry • Quantum Mechanics • Nuclear Materials • Object-Oriented Programming and Scientific Computing for Nuclear Science and Engineering • Radiation Transport and Shielding Design • Topics in Nuclear Science and Engineering 	Same as M.S., with optional project-based electives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Molten Salt Reactor Technology • Nuclear Risk Management • Nuclear Fuel Cycle • Dynamic Reactor Behavior and Intelligent Control • Computational Methods in Radiation Transport
Dual-Listed Math/Physics	Graduate-level content in applied mathematics and physics Additional problem sets and assignments for graduate students	Same as M.S.	Same as M.S., with potential for deeper integration into research
Hands-On	MSRR-based lab modules Capstone or thesis	MSRR-based design project or applied systems clinic	Independent reactor-centered research Dissertation defense
Certificate Modules (Future)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optional focused training in radiological safety, reactor operations, or environmental monitoring • To also be offered to non-degree-seeking candidates 	Same as M.S.	Same as M.S.

puts.

Hands-on learning is a core part of all the programs. Students will do lab work, participate in research related to the MSRR and NEXT Lab, may have opportunities for internships outside the university, and complete safety training before doing experiments. These experiences will help students gain skills and certifications that can lead to jobs in utilities, national labs, government agencies, or private research and development.

Strategic partnerships are planned to expand curricular breadth and internship pathways while faculty capacity scales. We are pursuing a four-university consortium to provide temporary course sharing to deliver specialized doctoral-level topics until future ACU faculty hires create permanent offerings. We will recruit industry and national lab partners to sponsor projects, provide internships, and mentor students alongside program faculty.

6. ASSESSMENT AND SUSTAINABILITY

The program will use a defined assessment system to track student learning, program quality, and operational effectiveness. We will track indicators such as enrollment and retention rates, time to degree, seminar participation, project or thesis completion, research publications, conference presentations, grant involvement, internship placements, and post-graduation employment in industry, laboratories, regulatory agencies, or academia. The primary focus areas include student learning outcomes, research productivity, experiential impact, student progression and placement, and resource availability.

Assessment methods will combine direct measures, e.g., graded deliverables, competency rubrics for core reactor and experimental skills, qualifying and comprehensive exams, thesis/project defenses, and portfolio reviews of lab competencies. It will also include indirect measures such as exit surveys, employer and partner feedback, alumni follow-up, and external reviewer commentary. We will collect data each semester, aggregate it annually, and review it with the Director and ACU Graduate Program and ultimately an external advisory committee; annual reports will compare outcomes against target thresholds (for example, cumulative GPA ≥ 3.0 , median time-to-MS ≤ 3 semesters) and prescribe curricular or resourcing adjustments. A five-year pro forma timeline developed within the program will serve as a formal review milestone to assess enrollment and funding assumptions, and to adjust hiring or partnership strategies if actual metrics deviate from projections.

Sustainability rests on three pillars: diversified revenue, staged faculty growth tied to funding milestones, and strategic partnership leverage. Revenue diversification emphasizes external research grants, certificate and continuing-education offerings, and targeted philanthropy for facility and chair support; conservative, increasing research income assumptions in the pro forma will guide the timing and scale of new hires. Faculty staffing follows a staged model: initial reliance on dual-listed courses and adjunct/consortium delivery to meet launch needs, recruit two tenure-track hires focused on graduate teaching and research before launch, and the addition of 1–2 faculty in 2028–2029 contingent on meeting funding expectations.

We will mitigate risks by including formal short-term shared-course agreements with partner universities to deliver specialized doctoral coursework, creation of relationships with industry and national laboratories to aid in internship placements and project sponsorships, and maintaining minimum operational reserves for core operations. Resource planning will monitor MSRR and NEXT Lab utilization, safety and compliance costs, and faculty workload to prevent negative impacts on related undergraduate programs.

Governance and accountability assign primary responsibility to the Program Director, supported by the ACU Graduate Program and the Onstead College of Science and Engineering, which will together review the pro forma benchmarks, grant pipeline, hiring triggers, and assessment outcomes. Assessment results will be explicitly linked to actions such as curricular revisions, hiring prioritization, stipend adjustments, and partnership renegotiation. Annual public summaries of program metrics will support transparency within the university, inform accreditation reporting, and guide fundraising and strategic decisions to ensure the curriculum remains aligned with workforce needs and the program's graduate education mission.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The NS&E graduate program has been developed to pair reactor-focused experiential training with rigorous coursework and professional development to meet workforce and research needs in advanced reactor technology and nuclear systems. At the time of this writing, both M.S. and M.Eng. programs have received full approval from ACU and SACSCOC. The Ph.D. Program Application has been completed and is currently under review at ACU; approval is anticipated this spring, with SACSCOC approval expected by June. ACU is accepting student applications for Fall 2026.

We are conducting faculty searches and arranging adjunct coverage where necessary to ensure curricular delivery during hiring. The assessment data pipeline and the five-year pro forma review will be implemented to validate enrollment, funding, and hiring assumptions and to guide iterative adjustments. With institutional decisions, regulatory approvals, and funding milestones in alignment, ACU is positioned to take the "NEXT" step toward launching a research-oriented graduate program that develops the next generation of nuclear leaders.

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